

The computational simulation and impact analysis of the rib bones

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Abstract

Ribs have crucial functions in the human body, most importantly provide protection to the vital inner organs such as heart and lungs. Yet the rib fractures are the most common bone fractures in blunt force accidents. Therefore, understanding more about the impact responses of the ribs is necessary. This study analyses the impact responses of the first and third ribs using the finite element method. A CT image of the thorax was used to obtain the geometric model of the individual ribs. Models with 3D tetrahedral meshes were created and appropriate boundary conditions were imposed. The material of the bone was considered elastic, isotropic and homogenous. The elasto-static analysis was conducted using FEMAS academic software. Distinct variable fields, such as displacement, von Mises equivalent stress, first and third principal stresses, were studied when a constant magnitude load is applied to three different points on the ribs, assuming two distinct directions. Displacement and stress variations along the inner and outer borders of each rib were analysed. Obtained results suggest that a load applied to the lateral region of the bone is the most acute case, showing the highest displacement and stress values. Thus, such findings, indicate the location of a possible fracture (or catastrophic damage) in both rib bones.

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1 Introduction

Rib cage provides protection and support to the human body. The heart and lungs are protected by the ribs. Hence rib fractures can lead to injuries in the internal organs causing severe situations. Rib fractures are regular in automobile crashes and fallings, and represent the most common bone fracture occurring in 10–20% of all blunt trauma patients [1]. However, uncomplicated single rib fractures can be managed easily but multiple rib fractures may result in a pneumothorax, a life-threatening emergency [2].

Humans have 24 ribs, in 12 pair. Each rib is a curved, flattened bone that contributes to the wall of the thorax. The superior ribs (1 to 3) are relatively protected by the scapula, clavicle, and soft tissue [3]. Ribs have 3 major regions namely posterior, anterior and lateral. The anterior extremity is connected to costal cartilages of the sternum and the posterior extremity is connected to the respective thoracic vertebra. The ribs are constituted by cortical and trabecular bones [4].

In the field of biomechanics, post- mortem human subject (PMHS) tests, anthropomorphic test devices (ATDs) and computational simulations have been applied over the years to analyse the structural variations of the ribs during impact. With recent developments in computational methods, such as finite element methods, meshless methods and other discrete numerical techniques, the use of computational models to simulate real scenarios has been increased. However, the accuracy of the computational methods mainly depends on the model quality, geometry and mechanical properties. Finite Element Method (FEM) is the most popular discrete technique used in modern biomechanical analysis. Automotive crash simulations and injury analyses are performed with different testing methods, mostly with full thoraces models, full-body models or lab models. When analysing the impact responses on rib bones, generally thoracic models or individual ribs have been used. However small-scale refined models are believed to represent an accurate geometric model since large scale models usually present an oversimplified geometry [5][6][7]. Past studies suggest that cortical bone thickness and cross-sectional geometry are important factors of rib impact response analysis, which can be achieved through FE models [8].

This study aims to analyse the impact responses of the first and third rib when loads are applied to different regions of the rib as well as in distinct directions. The Finite Element and Meshless Analysis Software (FEMAS) academic software (cmech.webs.com) was used to perform the structural analysis of the ribs.

2 Methodology and Materials

This study utilizes models of first and third ribs which were obtained from anonymized CT images of the thorax, which allows to acquire an accurate geometric model. CT image was converted into 3D solid meshes with tetrahedral elements for each separated rib.

A first rib model with 1531 nodes and 5417 elements and third rib model with 1253 nodes and 3815 elements were obtained. The human ribs consist of highly vascular cancellous bone, enclosed in a thin layer of cortical bone. Previous studies propose that human rib bones are anisotropic and viscoelastic [9][10]. However, since the cortical and cancellous bones have different material properties, their contribution to the whole rib properties are different as well. As Ayagara, 2019 explains, the cortical bone can be modelled as isotropic [11]. In another study conducted by Li et al., 2010, it was found that in human ribs, changes of trabecular bone properties has negligible influence on rib responses compared to cortical bone [12]. Hence, in this study, the rib models consist of a cortical bone shell with variable thickness, which is assumed to be elastic, isotropic and homogenous. The average mechanical properties were adopted from literature analysis ([7] [12] [13] [14]), as Young's modulus to be 13.9GPa and Poisson's ratio to be 0.3. Finally, the computational mechanical analysis was conducted on the two models using FEMAS academic software.

In each rib, three points were chosen, and a determined force was applied from two directions making 6 load cases, to analyse the loading impacts on the ribs. The analysed load cases consist of three loads applied in the Oz direction (F1, F2, F3) and another three loads applied in the Ox direction, (F4, F5, F6), as figures 1(b) and figure 2(b) show. All the applied loads possess the same absolute magnitude of 500N. As depicted in figure 1 a) and 2 a), both extremities of the ribs are fixed where the rib connects with the costal cartilage and thoracic vertebra, constraining the degrees of freedom off all nodes indicated in white. To analyse the regional variations of stresses and displacement, inner and outer border of the ribs, as indicated in figure 1 c) and figure 2 c), were selected.

Fig. 1 - First Rib bone (a) Boundary conditions (b) Applied load cases (c) Analysed regions

Fig. 2 - Third Rib bone (a) Boundary conditions (b) Applied load cases (c) Analysed regions.

3 Results

The elasto-static analysis was conducted on each rib using constant strain tetrahedral elements. Absolute displacement, Von Mises stress, first and third principal stresses were analysed in both ribs with 6 different load cases.

Figures 3 and 4 present the absolute displacements of the first and third ribs respectively, with their maximum and minimum values. The first rib reaches a maximum displacement of 0.55mm when F2 is applied (negative Oz -direction), 0.055mm is the lowest displacement reached by F6 (positive Ox -direction). The highest value of the third rib is 7.9 mm when the F2 is applied and 0.73 mm minimum displacement was reached when F4 is applied.

Fig. 3 - Displacement colour maps of the first rib with each load case from F1 to F6, respectively

Fig. 4 - Displacement colour maps of the third rib with each load case from F1 to F6, respectively.

In von Mises failure theory, it is considered that energy absorbed during the distortion is responsible for failure [15]. In this theory, if the stress exceeds the yield stress, failure occurs. Figures 5 and 6 present the von Mises stress from the first and third rib, respectively. A maximum of 52 MPa von Mises stress value was reached when the F1 is applied.

Minimum stress was obtained in the F3 with 30MPa. In the third rib, comparably high stresses can be observed with the maximum value of 270 MPa in F2 and the lowest value of 52 MPa when the F4 is applied. In most cases, the highest stress is concentrated on the rib where it connects with the rib cage (anterior and posterior articular facets).

Fig. 5 - Von Mises stresses of the first rib with each load case from F1 to F6, respectively.

Fig. 6 - Von Mises stresses of the third rib with each load case from F1 to F6, respectively.

Principal stresses in a complex 3D load case indicate the maximum and minimum normal stresses that a point reaches in a particular plane. The first principal stress indicates the highest value in an element and the lowest value is considered as the third principal stress. Figures 7 and 8 represent the first principal stresses and figures 9 and 10 present the third principal stresses. The first principal stress of the first rib (Figure 7), the F1 causes the highest maximum principal stress (71 MPa) and the lowest maximum stress were caused by the F6 (-4 MPa). The highest minimum principal stress of the

first rib is noted to be -59MPa (Compressive Stress) from F4 and the lowest minimum stress is 7 MPa from F6, as figure 9 shows.

Figure 8 includes the first principal stress of the third rib from load case F1 to F6. In the third rib, the highest both maximum and minimum stresses were obtained when the F2 applied, values being 370 MPa and -255 MPa, respectively. And the lowest both maximum and minimum stress were observed in the F4 with -13 MPa and 8 MPa, respectively, as in figure 10.

Fig. 7 - First principal stress of the first rib with each load case from F1 to F6, respectively.

Fig. 8 - First principal stress of the third rib with each load case from F1 to F6, respectively.

4 Discussion

This study was conducted to analyse the load impact on the first and third rib bone using the finite element method. Displacement, von Mises stress and principal stresses were obtained for each rib when 6 different load cases were applied. Analysing the results from the obtained figures, the third rib suffers considerably higher stresses and displacements than the first rib when enforced the same magnitude of loads. This can be expected since the first rib has a higher cross-sectional area compared with the third rib. In both ribs, the lateral section of the rib displaces more than the posterior or anterior ends in all load cases, mostly concentrated on the load applied point. The first rib seems to be having higher von Mises stress, first and third principal stresses in the tubercle articular facet of the rib. The third rib has its higher stresses in the sternal extremity.

Fig. 9 - Third principle stress of the first rib with each load case from F1 to F6, respectively.

Fig. 10 - Third principal stress of the third rib with each load case from F1 to F6, respectively

Furthermore, observing colour maps for the first rib, the F2 load is noted to impose the highest displacement and highest von Mises and first principal stress are inflicted by F1 and F2 load cases, F4 and F5 impose the highest third principal stresses. In the third rib, the highest displacement, highest von Mises stress, maximum first and third stresses were obtained when F2 applied. To obtain a clearer idea of the impact change of each load along the ribs, displacements and stresses were analysed along the points of both interior and exterior borders of each rib and graphed against the border length.

As seen in figures 11 and 12, the inner border of the first rib is less displaced, but allows higher von Mises, first and third principal stresses compared with the exterior border. In addition, it can be observed that in both borders the F2 and F5 load cases cause maximum displacement and higher stresses while F6 imposes the lowest values. F1, F3 and F4 load cases have occasional higher values mostly where the loads are applied. The load cases F1 and F2 are noted to have a higher displacement in both the inner and outer borders of the third rib. Higher von Mises, first and third principal stresses are caused by F1, F2 and F3 load cases. Moreover, F4, F5 and F6 loads have a relatively lower impact on the third rib, as presented in figure 13 and 14.

Fig. 11 - Structural analysis of the outer region of the first rib (a) Displacement (b) von Mises stress (c) First principal stress (d) Third principal stress, graphed against the distance from the first point.

5 Conclusion

Results were studied by enforcing the same magnitude load on 3 different points with two directions on each rib bone. In the first rib, the severer load was found to be F1 having maximum von Mises stress and first principal stress. Furthermore, F2 load case is having relatively higher stresses. The highest displacement was caused when a load applied to the lateral region of the rib (F2 and F5). Loads applied to the anterior region are noted to cause the least impact.

In the third rib, unlike the first rib, the severe load case depends more on the applied direction rather than the position. It was noted that loads applied from Ox-direction had a higher impact on bone than the Oz-direction. The most acute load case was applied to the lateral position of the rib, F2. Meanwhile, in both ribs, the outer border suffers higher displacement and higher stresses than on the inner border.

There are a few limitations regarding the model and properties used in this study. Constant material properties were used throughout the rib but in reality, the Young's modulus might vary in the lateral, posterior and anterior regions of the rib [16].

Fig. 12 - Structural analysis of the inner region of the first rib (a) Displacement (b) von Mises stress (c) First principal stress (d) Third principal stress, graphed against the distance from the first point.

Fig. 13 - Structural analysis of the outer region of the third rib (a) Displacement (b) von Mises stress (c) First principal stress (d) Third principal stress, graphed against the distance from the first point.

Fig. 14 - Structural analysis of the inner region of the third rib (a) Displacement (b) von Mises stress (c) First principal stress (d) Third principal stress, graphed against the distance from the first point.

Soft tissues and internal organs also affect the impact responses of the ribs, hence ribs have complex 3-dimensional boundary conditions, which are complex to simulate. The bone mechanical properties were assumed to be elastic, homogenous and isotropic. Despite these limitations, this study has shown that it is possible to use open source software to perform computational analysis of impact testing of individual ribs.

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